

Commercial hormone replacement therapy jeopardized pro-inflammatory factors in experimental rat models

La terapia de reemplazo hormonal comercial puso en peligro los factores proinflamatorios en modelos experimentales de ratas

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Abstract

hormone replacement therapy is considered the easiest and most convenient contraceptive method. Commercially available contraceptive combination differs in their composition and concentration of combined constituents. These variations make some of these products preferred over others by consumers based on their side effects profile. The objective of the current research was to ascertain the pro-inflammatory influences of commercially available products. To do so, five groups of rats (ten rats each group) were exposed to Microgynon, Depo-Provera, Marvelon, and Yasmin compared to the control non-treated group. We measured pro-inflammatory markers including d-dimer, TNF- α (tumour necrosis factor-alpha), IL(interleukin)-6, IL(interleukin)-1B, and CRP (c-reactive protein). The results confirmed that Yasmin has induced the most deleterious effects on pro-inflammatory markers indicated by significant elevation of IL1B. In conclusion, hormone replacement therapy should be critically indicated and precaution raised inpatient with subclinical diseases, especially cardiovascular ones.

Keywords: estrogen, progesterone, contraceptive, hormone replacement, interleukin, C-reactive protein.

Resumen

la terapia de reemplazo hormonal se considera el método anticonceptivo más fácil y conveniente. La combinación anticonceptiva comercialmente disponible difiere en su composición y concentración de componentes combinados. Estas variaciones hacen que algunos de estos productos sean preferidos por los consumidores sobre otros en función de su perfil de efectos secundarios. El objetivo de la investigación actual fue determinar las influencias proinflamatorias de los productos disponibles comercialmente. Para hacerlo, cinco grupos de ratas (diez ratas cada grupo) fueron expuestos a Microgynon, Depo-Provera, Marvelon y Yasmin en comparación con el grupo de control no tratado. Medimos marcadores proinflamatorios que incluyen dímero D, TNF- α (factor de necrosis tumoral alfa), IL (interleucina)-6, IL (interleucina)-1B y PCR (proteína c reactiva). Los resultados confirmaron que Yasmin ha inducido los efectos más nocivos sobre los marcadores proinflamatorios indicados por una elevación significativa de IL1B. En conclusión, la terapia de reemplazo hormonal debe ser una indicación crítica y una precaución en pacientes con enfermedades subclínicas, especialmente cardiovasculares.

Palabras clave: estrógeno, progesterona, anticonceptivo, reemplazo hormonal, interleucina, proteína C reactiva.

544

Introduction

Estrogen therapy during the post-menopausal increases the "hepatic production of C-Reactive Protein (CRP)"¹, and the representation of IL-6 increases and plays an inflammatory role². It has been illustrated the contrary results for Estradiol^{3,4} used in postmenopause. Bestowing to an earlier conducted study progesterone increases the sequel of experimental

stroke⁵, however, an alternative study clarifies that progestins resolves "oxidative stress" and relegates generating of IL-6 and TNF- α ⁶.

In the western world, vascular diseases are a huge health care burden and a considerable increase in aging is ob-

served⁷. This risk is increased only in women alongside aging without caring about the well-known sex difference in cardiovascular diseases^{8,9}. The post-menopausal decrease in ovarian hormones can also be the contributing factor, which can have impacts on many tissues alongside vasculature^{7,10}. The beneficial effect of estrogen on “cerebrovascular function” has constantly been shown in observational studies and experimental animal research¹⁰. However, a large number of “randomized clinical trials” raised questions about the benefits of “hormone-replacement therapy (HRT)”, and in fact, they detect an increase in stroke¹¹⁻¹³.

These diversified verdicts played a role to mention the necessity for improved comprehension of vascular actions of “ovarian hormones” alongside the understanding of “medroxyprogesterone acetate (MPA)”; a “synthetic analog of progesterone”. It is usually instructed to use in a mixture with estrogen for the treatment of “perimenopausal symptoms”. Having benefits, it MPA also has some back draws. According to some studies, MPA can also withstand the favorable influences of “estrogen on cardiovascular” functions and operations¹⁴⁻¹⁶. Talking about example, MPA has positive effects on estrogen biomedical metabolism, vasculature system, and advancement of atherosclerosis¹⁴.

The pathogenesis of “cerebral ischemia”¹⁷ is mainly caused by “cerebrovascular inflammation”¹⁸. The induction of promotion of inflammation mediators alongside the inclusion of inducible nitric oxide synthase and cyclooxygenase^{19,20} are the lead process in “cerebrovascular inflammation”. Cyclooxygenase is upregulated during cerebral ischemia which results in the generation of prostanoids, such as PGE₂, and are considered to be harmful to stroke outcomes²¹. After cerebral ischemic injury²² expression of iNOS is increased and its peak is shown in 24-48 hours. No production is thought to have either beneficial or detrimental effects following ischemia, quantities are produced and the stage of “evolution of cerebral injury”²²⁻²⁴ depends on the cellular compartment.

Estrogen has constructive influences in paradigms of cardiovascular damage¹⁰ according to experimental animal studies.

While effects of progestagens “cerebrovascular inflammation” are still unknown. To answer this question, rat models were used in the in vivo progestagen treatment, which is just a reflection of known clinical blood levels²⁵. During the process, the unpredicted unfavorable effects of combined HRT on stroke were seen²⁶, researchers assumed that progestagens, progesterone, or MPA, undo the influences of estrogen on inflammation. They also assumed the normal alteration in “endogenous estrogen” and progesterone and that caused alteration in cerebrovascular inflammation throughout the estrous cycle.

To begin, a lot of controversies exist using progesterone in systematic inflammation. To check the different effects of “estradiol and progesterone” on the “inflammatory and apoptotic responses” in rat models using commercially available estrogen-progesterone combination products, the present study was created.

Materials and methods

To carry out this research, a total of thirty healthy female “Wistar albino rats” with the age age 10-12 weeks and weight 200–260gm, were collected from the “animal house of Medical Research Institute in University of Mosul”, the period of the study ranges from 1/1/2020 to 1/12/2020. Then, animals were endorsed in the “animal house of Mosul University” and were avowed under meticulous settings of temperature (24 ± 2°C), “light-dark periods” of 12 hours, and with free access to water and commercial diet^{26,27,28}.

Next, the “international guiding principles” for biomedical research involving animals were adopted. The animals were administered a four-week adaptation period after they were located in their new environment. The animals were divided into five groups, ten rats each. Control group, Microgynon® group, Depo-Provera group, Marvelon group, Yasmin® group. The dose administration is listed in table 1.

Table 1. Specification of used drugs.

Trade name	Composition		Manufacturer	Origin	Administration and Dosing schedules
	Progestin	Estrogen			
Microgynon pills	Levonorgestrel (0.15 mg/kg)	Ethinylestradiol (0.03 mg/kg)	Bayer	Germany	Orally for 4 days; one day break for 8 weeks
Depo-Provera injection	Medroxyprogesterone (3.5 mg/rat)		Pfizer	USA	I.M.; once weekly for 8 weeks
Marvelon pills	Desogestrel (0.15 mg/kg)	Ethinylestradiol (0.03 mg/kg)	MSD	USA	Orally for 4 days; one day break for 8 weeks
Yasmin pills	Drospirenone (0.5mg/kg)	Ethinylestradiol (0.03 mg/kg)	Bayer	Germany	Orally for 4 days; one day break for 8 weeks)

MSD= Merck and Co. Inc.

Finally, the serum sample analysis was carried out for measured parameters using ELISA technique. The results of samples were statistically analyzed and comparison was conducted between Microgynon, Depo-Provera, Marvelon, and Yasmin group compared to the control group.

Results and discussion

Regarding CRP, all studied groups show the same level of CRP (0.16 ng/ml) which is considered a normal level.

Regarding D-dimer levels (ng/ml), non-significant differences exist between all studied groups (levels are approximate to 200ng/ml) except for the Yasmin group at 8-weeks' time point where the level show significant ($p < 0.05$) elevation to reach 380.6 ± 19 compared to control or other groups at same time points.

Regarding IL-1B levels (pg/ml), non-significant differences exist between baseline and week-4 timepoints in all studied groups (levels are approximate to 200ng/ml) except for Marvelon which showed significant differences at week-4. However, at week-8 timepoints, all studied groups show significantly higher IL-1B levels compared to baseline except for Depo-Provera which showed non-significant differences with baseline levels.

Figure 1. Hormonal upset in rats treated by commercially available contraceptive medicines; Microgynon (M), Depo-Provera (D), Marvelon (Mv), and Yasmin (Y). Data expressed as mean $\pm$ SD. * $p < 0.05$ Yasmin compared to baseline, # $p < 0.05$ Marvelon compared to baseline, and \$ $p < 0.05$ Microgynon compared to baseline.

The present study confirmed that hormonal replacement therapy carries a pro-inflammatory risk. The study findings support this statement as confirmed by measured pro-inflammatory markers. However, there have been discrepancies in the outcomes when these commercial products are compared to each other. Compared to 4-weeks, the proinflammatory defect was more obvious at 8-weeks, if any. Yasmin

pills have shown the most deleterious defect compared to Microgynon, Marvelon, and Depo-Provera. Yasmin induced significantly higher D-dimer and IL-6. Surprisingly, Yasmin-induced IL-6 elevation was acute since the elevation was obvious in 4-weeks, and the level reduced to baseline after 8 weeks. This effect interestingly might confirm that tolerance to Yasmin IL-6 proinflammatory effects might be produced. Yasmin induced significantly higher pro-inflammatory status, indicated by higher IL-6 at week 4 and elevated IL-1B, D-dimer at week 8. The second deleterious agent was Marvelon; which was associated

Obvious changes were seen after the treatment which continued for 4 weeks²⁹ and before that, two large "observational studies"^{30,31} and two clinical trials³⁰⁻³² "significant elevations" in CRP in women who are taking replacement therapy (48-260% higher than in non-users). CRP hepatic formation is chiefly conducted to the promotion of inflammation cytokine IL-6³³. Elevated levels of CRP are possibly linked with cardiovascular events in healthy subjects³⁴⁻³⁸ and also in the subjects with established vascular disease^{35,36, 39,40}.

HRT was considered that increase in CRP was caused by "systematic inflammation" but it was the cause of direct hepatic passing of oral estrogen³⁹. In evidential form, they showed that plasma IL-6 levels were quite similar to the estrogen users and in the non-user women who were CHD free or in the individuals whom CHD eventually developed⁴¹⁻⁴⁴.

Reduction of "TNF- α expression by progesterone" in a rat model of brain injury was reported by Jiang et al⁴⁵ where conflicted data with the findings of researchers were also observed. At the same time, Roof et al⁴⁶ revealed that the "membrane-stabilizing effect" can also reduce oxidative stress by progesterone. Estradiol reduces the "TNF- α expression" in female rats managed with "a combination of progesterone and estradiol"^{44,47} and estradiol also protects the CNS against neurotoxic stimuli. But this finding contradicts the finding of our research, that highlighted by the anti-inflammatory role of estradiol⁴⁷.

Figure 1

Conclusion

The outcome confirmed that sex hormone medicines has jeopardized the proinflammatory marker, showing variation between the outcome when different brands were used. Yasmin has the utmost deleterious outcome compared to others while Depo-Provera was the safest product.

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References

- Jing L, Wu N, He L, Shao J, Ma H. Establishment of an experimental rat model of high altitude cerebral edema by hypobaric hypoxia combined with temperature fluctuation. *Brain Research Bulletin*. 2020 Dec 1;165:253-62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.brainres-bull.2020.10.017>
- Herrington DM, Brosnihan KB, Pusser BE, Seely EW, Ridker PM, Rifai N, MacLean DB. Differential effects of E and droloxifene on C-reactive protein and other markers of inflammation in healthy postmenopausal women. *The Journal of Clinical Endocrinology & Metabolism*. 2001 Sep 1;86(9):4216-22. <https://doi.org/10.1210/jcem.86.9.7799>
- Panazzolo DG, da Silva LH, Maranhão PA, Souza MG, Nogueira Neto JF, Leao LM, Bouskela E, Kraemer-Aguiar LG. Short-term effects of low-dose estradiol on endothelial function and blood viscosity in nondiabetic postmenopausal overweight women: a double-blind, placebo-controlled study. *Menopause*. 2016 Oct 1;23(10):1114-21. <https://doi.org/10.1097/GME.0000000000000686>
- Sunday L, Tran MM, Krause DN, Duckles SP. Estrogen and progestagens differentially modulate vascular proinflammatory factors. *American Journal of Physiology-Endocrinology and Metabolism*. 2006 Aug;291(2):E261-7. <https://doi.org/10.1152/ajpendo.00550.2005>
- Szabó R, Karácsonyi Z, Börzsei D, Juhász B, Al-Awar A, Török S, Berkó AM, Takács I, Kupai K, Varga C, Pósa A. Role of exercise-induced cardiac remodeling in ovariectomized female rats. *Oxidative medicine and cellular longevity*. 2018 Feb 13;2018.
- Aksoy AN, Toker A, Celik M, Aksoy M, Halıcı Z, Aksoy H. The effect of progesterone on systemic inflammation and oxidative stress in the rat model of sepsis. *Indian Journal of Pharmacology*. 2014 Nov;46(6):622. doi: 10.4103/0253-7613.144922
- Mansoori MN, Raghuvanshi A, Shukla P, Awasthi P, Trivedi R, Goel A, Singh D. Medicaipin prevents arthritis in post-menopausal conditions by arresting the expansion of TH17 cells and pro-inflammatory cytokines. *International Immunopharmacology*. 2020 May 1;82:106299. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intimp.2020.106299>
- Isles CG, Hole DJ, Hawthorne VM, Lever AF. Relation between coronary risk and coronary mortality in women of the Renfrew and Paisley survey: comparison with men. *The Lancet*. 1992 Mar 21;339(8795):702-6. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0140-6736\(92\)90599-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0140-6736(92)90599-X)
- Wu Q, Kling JM. Depression and the risk of myocardial infarction and coronary death: a meta-analysis of prospective cohort studies. *Medicine*. 2016 Feb;95(6). <https://doi.org/10.1097%2FMD.0000000000002815>
- Hurn PD, Brass LM. Estrogen and stroke: a balanced analysis. *Stroke*. 2003 Feb 1;34(2):338-41. <https://doi.org/10.1161/01.STR.0000054051.88378.25>
- Brass LM. Hormone replacement therapy and stroke: clinical trials review. *Stroke*. 2004 Nov 1;35(11_suppl_1):2644-7. <https://doi.org/10.1161/01.STR.0000143218.20061.ac>
- Hulley S, Grady D, Bush T, Furberg C, Herrington D, Riggs B, Vittinghoff E. Randomized Trial of Estrogen Plus Progestin for Secondary Prevention of Coronary Heart Disease in Postmenopausal Women. *Obstetrical & gynecological survey*. 1999 Jan 1;54(1):41-2.
- Guo H, Liu M, Zhang L, Wang L, Hou W, Ma Y, Ma Y. The critical period for neuroprotection by estrogen replacement therapy and the potential underlying mechanisms. *Current Neuropharmacology*. 2020 Jun 1;18(6):485-500. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1570159X18666200123165652>
- Clarkson TB. Progestogens and cardiovascular disease. A critical review. *The Journal of Reproductive Medicine*. 1999 Feb 1;44(2 Suppl):180-4.
- Darby A. "Risks and Benefits of Estrogen Plus Progestin in Healthy, Postmenopausal Women: Principal Results from the Women's Health Initiative Randomized Controlled Trial"(2002), by Jacques Rossouw et al. *Embryo Project Encyclopedia*. 2017 Aug 8.
- Simon JA, Hsia J, Cauley JA, Richards C, Harris F, Fong J, Barrett-Connor E, Hulley SB. Postmenopausal hormone therapy and risk of stroke: The Heart and Estrogen/progestin Replacement Study (HERS). *Circulation*. 2001 Feb 6;103(5):638-42. <https://doi.org/10.1161/01.CIR.103.5.638>
- Yang C, Hawkins KE, Doré S, Candelario-Jalil E. Neuroinflammatory mechanisms of blood-brain barrier damage in ischemic stroke. *American Journal of Physiology-Cell Physiology*. 2019 Feb 1;316(2):C135-53. <https://doi.org/10.1152/ajpcell.00136.2018>
- Del Zoppo G, Ginis I, Hallenbeck JM, Iadecola C, Wang X, Feuerstein GZ. Inflammation and stroke: putative role for cytokines, adhesion molecules and iNOS in brain response to ischemia. *Brain pathology*. 2000 Jan;10(1):95-112. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1750-3639.2000.tb00247.x>
- McKay LI, Cidlowski JA. Molecular control of immune/inflammatory responses: interactions between nuclear factor- κ B and steroid receptor-signaling pathways. *Endocrine reviews*. 1999 Aug 1;20(4):435-59.
- Li Q, Tian Z, Wang M, Kou J, Wang C, Rong X, Li J, Xie X, Pang X. Lutealolide attenuates neuroinflammation in focal cerebral ischemia in rats via regulation of the PPAR γ /Nrf2/NF- κ B signaling pathway. *International Immunopharmacology*. 2019 Jan 1;66:309-16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intimp.2018.11.044>
- Iadecola C, Forster C, Nogawa S, Clark HB, Ross ME. Cyclooxygenase-2 immunoreactivity in the human brain following cerebral ischemia. *Acta neuropathologica*. 1999 Jun;98(1):9-14. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s004010051045>
- Iadecola C, Zhang F, Casey RJ, Nagayama M, Ross ME. Delayed reduction of ischemic brain injury and neurological deficits in mice lacking the inducible nitric oxide synthase gene. *Journal of Neuroscience*. 1997 Dec 1;17(23):9157-64. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.17-23-09157.1997>
- Dawson VL, Dawson TM. Nitric oxide in neurodegeneration. *Progress in brain research*. 1998 Jan 1;118:215-29. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0079-6123\(08\)63210-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0079-6123(08)63210-0)
- Ospina JA, Brevig HN, Krause DN, Duckles SP. Estrogen suppresses IL-1 β -mediated induction of COX-2 pathway in rat cerebral blood

vessels. *American Journal of Physiology-Heart and Circulatory Physiology*. 2004 May;286(5):H2010-9. <https://doi.org/10.1152/ajp-heart.00481.2003>

25. McNeill AM, Zhang C, Stanczyk FZ, Duckles SP, Krause DN. Estrogen increases endothelial nitric oxide synthase via estrogen receptors in rat cerebral blood vessels: effect preserved after concurrent treatment with medroxyprogesterone acetate or progesterone. *Stroke*. 2002 Jun 1;33(6):1685-91. <https://doi.org/10.1161/01.STR.0000016325.54374.93>
26. Swica Y, Warren MP, Manson JE, Aragaki AK, Bassuk SS, Shimbo D, Kaunitz A, Rossouw J, Stefanick ML, Womack CR. Effects of oral conjugated equine estrogens with or without medroxyprogesterone acetate on incident hypertension in the Women's Health Initiative hormone therapy trials. *Menopause (New York, NY)*. 2018 Jul;25(7):753. <https://doi.org/10.1097%2FGME.0000000000001067>
27. Sada W, Abdulqader, Ibrahim M, Faisal, M. G. Saeed, Marwan M, Merkhan. Fluvoxamine Suppressed Oxidative Stress associated with Tissue Erosion. *Research Journal of Pharmacy and Technology*. 2022; 15(2):819-4. DOI: 10.5958/0974-360X
28. Abdulqader SW, Faisal IM, Saeed MG, Merkhan MM. Fluvoxamine Provide a Gastro-Protection Against Vitiated Insult. *Indian Journal of Forensic Medicine & Toxicology*. 2022 Jan;16(1):1047.
29. Bhuiyan FR, Hossain IA, Jahan K, Ali L. Effects of Soymilk on Serum Insulinemic Status and High Sensitivity C-Reactive Protein Levels in Healthy Postmenopausal Women of Bangladesh. *Food and Nutrition Sciences*. 2022 Apr 12;13(4):337-48. <https://doi.org/10.4236/fns.2022.134025>
30. Ridker PM, Hennekens CH, Rifai N, Buring JE, Manson JE. Hormone replacement therapy and increased plasma concentration of C-reactive protein. *Circulation*. 1999 Aug 17;100(7):713-6. <https://doi.org/10.1161/01.CIR.100.7.713>
31. Cushman M, Meilahn EN, Psaty BM, Kuller LH, Dobs AS, Tracy RP. Hormone replacement therapy, inflammation, and hemostasis in elderly women. *Arteriosclerosis, thrombosis, and vascular biology*. 1999 Apr;19(4):893-9. <https://doi.org/10.1161/01.ATV.19.4.893>
32. Kushner I. Regulation of the acute phase response by cytokines. *Perspectives in biology and medicine*. 1993;36(4):611-22. 10.1353/pbm.1993.0004
33. Cushman M, Legault C, Barrett-Connor E, Stefanick ML, Kessler C, Judd HL, Sakkinen PA, Tracy RP. Effect of postmenopausal hormones on inflammation-sensitive proteins: the Postmenopausal Estrogen/Progestin Interventions (PEPI) Study. *Circulation*. 1999 Aug 17;100(7):717-22. <https://doi.org/10.1161/01.CIR.100.7.717>
34. Simone Taylor S, Hennekens C. Interrelationships of periodontal disease, systemic inflammation, and cardiovascular disease. *Ann Dentist Oral Disord*. 2018;2:108.
35. Tracy RP, Lemaitre RN, Psaty BM, Ives DG, Evans RW, Cushman M, Meilahn EN, Kuller LH. Relationship of C-reactive protein to risk of cardiovascular disease in the elderly: results from the Cardiovascular Health Study and the Rural Health Promotion Project. *Arteriosclerosis, thrombosis, and vascular biology*. 1997 Jun;17(6):1121-7. <https://doi.org/10.1161/01.ATV.17.6.1121>
36. Kosmidou I, Redfors B, Chen S, Crowley A, Lembo NJ, Karmaliotis D, Brown III WM, Maupas E, Durrleman N, Shah A, Reardon MJ. C-reactive protein and prognosis after percutaneous coronary intervention and bypass graft surgery for left main coronary artery disease: analysis from the EXCEL trial. *American Heart Journal*. 2019 Apr 1;210:49-57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ahj.2018.12.013>
37. Ridker PM, Rifai N, Pfeffer MA, Sacks FM, Moye LA, Goldman S, Flaker GC, Braunwald E. Inflammation, pravastatin, and the risk of coronary events after myocardial infarction in patients with average cholesterol levels. *Circulation*. 1998 Sep 1;98(9):839-44. <https://doi.org/10.1161/01.CIR.98.9.839>
38. Koenig W, Sund M, Fröhlich M, Fischer HG, Löwel H, Döring A, Hutchinson WL, Pepys MB. C-Reactive protein, a sensitive marker of inflammation, predicts future risk of coronary heart disease in initially healthy middle-aged men: results from the MONICA (Monitoring Trends and Determinants in Cardiovascular Disease) Augsburg Cohort Study, 1984 to 1992. *Circulation*. 1999 Jan 19;99(2):237-42. <https://doi.org/10.1161/01.CIR.99.2.237>
39. Oyaque CE, Tapia ME, Oyaque TA, Torres CE. Factores de riesgo y predictores de preeclampsia: una mirada al futuro. *Revista Latinoamericana de Hipertensión*. 2018;13(1):6-12.
40. Zimmermann J, Herrlinger S, Pruy A, Metzger T, Wanner C. Inflammation enhances cardiovascular risk and mortality in hemodialysis patients. *Kidney international*. 1999 Feb 1;55(2):648-58. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1523-1755.1999.00273.x>
41. Pradhan AD, Manson JE, Rossouw JE, Siscovick DS, Mouton CP, Rifai N, Wallace RB, Jackson RD, Pettinger MB, Ridker PM. Inflammatory biomarkers, hormone replacement therapy, and incident coronary heart disease: prospective analysis from the Women's Health Initiative observational study. *Jama*. 2002 Aug 28;288(8):980-7. doi:10.1001/jama.288.8.980
42. Ortiz R, Bermúdez V, Lozada JA, Palacios JS, Ordoñez MG, Guzmán JS, Rodas EL, Caceres TM, Diaz CI, Zambrano AD, Ordoñez MG. Hipertensión arterial y su comportamiento epidemiológico en la población rural de Cumbe, Ecuador. *Revista Latinoamericana de Hipertensión*. 2017;12(5):109-18.
43. Herrington DM, Brosnihan KB, Pusser BE, Seely EW, Ridker PM, Rifai N, MacLean DB. Differential effects of E and droloxifene on C-reactive protein and other markers of inflammation in healthy postmenopausal women. *The Journal of Clinical Endocrinology & Metabolism*. 2001 Sep 1;86(9):4216-22. <https://doi.org/10.1210/jcem.86.9.7799>
44. Ortiz R, Torres M, Cordero SP, Lara VA, Torres MS, Procel XV, Añez RJ, Rojas J, Bermúdez V. Factores de riesgo asociados a hipertensión arterial en la población rural de Quinceo Ecuador. *Revista Latinoamericana de Hipertensión*. 2017;12(3):95-103.
45. Jiang C, Wang J, Li X, Liu C, Chen N, Hao Y. Progesterone exerts neuroprotective effects by inhibiting inflammatory response after stroke. *Inflammation research*. 2009 Sep;58(9):619-24. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00011-009-0032-8>
46. Roof RL, HALL ED. Gender differences in acute CNS trauma and stroke: neuroprotective effects of estrogen and progesterone. *Journal of neurotrauma*. 2000 May;17(5):367-88. <https://doi.org/10.1089/neu.2000.17.367>
47. Vegeto E, Benedusi V, Maggi A. Estrogen anti-inflammatory activity in brain: a therapeutic opportunity for menopause and neurodegenerative diseases. *Frontiers in neuroendocrinology*. 2008 Oct 1;29(4):507-19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yfrne.2008.04.001>